

EXPERIMENTALLY DETERMINING THE VISCOELASTIC BEHAVIOR OF A CURING THERMOSET EPOXY

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Abstract

The success of process models used to predict composite manufacturing largely depends on the quality of the material model input. High fidelity material models are necessary if accurate predictions are to be made using process models. Furthermore, the fidelity of a material model is dependent on the quality of the experimental data used for fitting. Many process models currently employed, such as those used to predict flow and stress during manufacturing of composite structures, are independent of each other. Despite their independence, often they must be coupled since the prediction of one model may be required as input for the other. Additionally, the material properties required as inputs into the flow and stress models, namely viscosity and modulus, are also currently treated separately in state of art process modeling software. Developments such as the integrated stress-flow formulation [1] require a consistent material model to predict the material behavior from viscous fluid to viscoelastic solid.

The aim of this work is to take a step towards an integrated viscosity and modulus description using a viscoelastic material model framework. Presented here is the experimental approach as well as the results of tests used to determine the viscoelastic behavior of a curing thermoset epoxy covering the evolution from pre-gelation liquid to fully cured glassy solid. The results show continuity between the viscous behavior as measured by a rheometer and the viscoelastic solid behavior as measured by a dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMTA). This experimental methodology and the resulting data set could be used to develop and fit a viscoelastic material model to all degrees of cure and temperatures encountered in a typical thermoset

manufacturing process. Examination of the results indicates that a simple horizontal shift, as used in a thermo-rheologically simple time-temperature-superposition, is not sufficient to describe the viscoelastic behavior of a curing epoxy. Additionally, the results show that the storage modulus of a glassy epoxy is independent of the material's degree of cure.

1 Introduction

Although the fundamental theory of viscoelasticity provides for models (e.g. Generalized Maxwell) to predict both viscosity and storage modulus [2], such models do not appear to exist in practice. One significant reason may be due to the challenge of generating experimental data across all temperature, time scales (or frequencies) and degree of cure (DOC) that are typically encountered during composite manufacturing processes. Further adding difficulty to characterization is that the material properties can vary by approximately 8 orders of magnitude from the GPa range to the Pa range, requiring different test setups. As a result, different equipment must be used to generate reliable data with accurate absolute values of viscosity and storage modulus.

Characterizing the viscoelastic solid behavior of polymers is typically done using a dynamic mechanical analyzer. Likewise, characterization of viscous fluids is typically done using a rheometer. Both of these analytical devices function fundamentally in the same manner. In both, force and displacement measurements (as well as sample geometry and dimensions) are used to calculate material properties. The force applied can be as a constant (such as in creep or rotational viscosity

tests) or in a sinusoidal fashion. However, the rheometer and DMTA deform the material in very different modes as required by the different material states.

2 Experiments

Three types of analytical equipment were used in this study; DMTA (Dynamic Mechanical and Thermal Analyzer, rheometer and DSC (Differential Scanning Calorimeter). Additionally, the previously developed NCAMP MTM45-1 cure kinetics model was used [3] and was implemented using RAVEN3 software [4]. All tests were performed on the commercially available MTM45-1. Both neat resin and prepreg (HTS5630 fiber) forms were tested.

2.1 Dynamic Mechanical and Thermal Analysis

DMTA tests were completed using a TA Instruments Q800 with 3-point bend geometry. Tests were performed with temperature ramps of 2°C/min and constant frequency of 1Hz on samples that had been prepared to varying DOC. Samples were manufactured by stacking uni-directional prepreg to a thickness of approximately 0.75 mm. The laminates were partially cured to achieve a glass transition temperature (T_g) slightly above room temperature ($DOC > 0.2$). The goal was to cure the samples to the lowest DOC possible, while still facilitating cutting and handling. The partially cured laminates were cut to length and width of 55mm and 8 mm respectively using a Buehler IsoMet4000 linear precision diamond saw. Samples were cut such that they were loaded in the 2-direction of the laminate. The DOC of each sample was determined using the DSC and the NCAMP material model and is detailed in section 2.3. Figure 1 shows a DMTA 3-point bend fixture and a prepreg sample.

During DMTA tests, storage modulus and loss modulus were captured while ramping the temperature from -30°C to just below the material's T_g . Data could not be collected above the material's instantaneous T_g since the sample would deform due to creep and also since significant cure progression would occur. Figure 2 shows the results of the storage modulus and figure 3 shows the results of

loss modulus for samples ranging in DOC from 0.27 to 0.99. In an effort to reduce the experimental error caused by sample to sample variability, the same sample was used for all temperature ramps with the exception of datasets for DOC of 0.82, 0.89 and 0.99. This was achieved by stopping the test before the temperature reached T_g of the material beyond which appreciable creep and cure progression would occur. After the DMTA test was complete, the samples were heated to activate curing in order to achieve a slightly higher DOC. During each cure advancement step, minor creep of the samples from the previous test was recovered (stress history removed). It was not possible to recover the creep in the sample with a $DOC > 0.75$ without completely curing the material. This was the reason a new sample was used for each of the tests at the higher DOC values. The NCAMP model implemented in RAVEN3 was used to design the post cure cycles to incrementally progress the sample DOC. After each post cure cycle, a small section of the end of the sample was cut off and tested in the DSC to determine the material DOC (detailed in section 2.3).

2.2 Rheological Tests

Rheological tests were performed on uncured neat resin samples using a TA Instruments AR2000 rheometer. Parallel plate geometry was used and all tests were conducted in oscillatory shear at a frequency of 1Hz and strain of 1%. Both isothermal and dynamic temperature ramp tests were performed. The isothermal tests were heated at a rate of 5°C/min to varied hold temperature of 125°C, 130°C, 135°C, 140°C and 145°C. Figure 4 and 5 show the results of the shear storage and loss modulus respectively for the isothermal rheometer tests. Dynamic temperature ramp tests were performed at 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5°C/min. Figure 6 and 7 show the results of the shear storage and loss modulus respectively for the temperature ramp rheometer tests.

2.3 Differential Scanning Calorimeter

A TA Instruments Q2000 was used to perform DSC analysis for this study. DSC tests were performed on material taken from each DMTA sample to determine its DOC. Modulated temperature ramps

were performed to measure the reversing heat capacity (C_p) of each sample. T_g was taken as the inflection point on the C_p curve. The DOC was then determined by referencing the DeBenedetto curve from the NCAMP model.

3 Data Reduction

In order to compare results from the DMTA and the rheometer, assumptions and calculations were made. Firstly, the magnitude of the resin extensional complex modulus $|E_m^*|$ was calculated from the magnitude of the extensional complex modulus of the prepreg $|E_2^*|$ using a rule of mixtures as follows

$$|E_2^*| = \frac{|E_m^*| \cdot |E_{f(transverse)}^*|}{|E_{f(transverse)}^*| \cdot (1 + V_f) + |E_m^*| \cdot V_f}$$

where $|E_{f(transverse)}^*|$ is the transverse fiber complex modulus and V_f is the fiber volume fraction. A value of 20GPa was used for $|E_{f(transverse)}^*|$ [5] and 0.589 was used for V_f [6]. It was assumed that the fiber is perfectly elastic and therefore the magnitude of the complex modulus is the same as the elastic modulus (zero loss modulus contribution). Secondly the magnitude of the shear complex modulus of the resin $|G_R^*|$ was calculated using Hooke's law

$$|G_R^*| = \frac{|E_r^*|}{2 \cdot (1 + \nu_r)}$$

where ν_R is the resin Poisson's ratio [7]. A constant Poisson's ratio of 0.36 was used [7][8]. It is important to note that both the rule of mixtures and Hooke's law have been applied to viscoelastic properties (complex modulus). Finally, the shear loss modulus (G''_R) and shear storage modulus (G'_R) components of the complex modulus were calculated assuming that the phase angle is the same for the resin and prepreg samples using

$$G'_R = |G_R^*| \cdot \cos(\delta)$$

$$G''_R = |G_R^*| \cdot \sin(\delta)$$

where δ is the phase angle.

For rheometry data, the only calculations performed was using the cure kinetics model to calculate the DOC for each data point. This enabled plotting the material properties as a function of temperature for constant DOC. Figures 8 and 9 shows the storage and loss modulus results from the rheometer as a function of temperature and grouped in constant DOC series.

4 Results

Overlaying the results from the DMTA and rheometer shows the effect of DOC and temperature on the resin viscoelastic response. Figure 10 and 11 plot G' and G'' respectively as a function of temperature. Each series is a constant DOC. In both of these figures, there is a region (10^5 to 10^7 Pa) where no data was generated. This was due to the limit of the torque that could be applied by the rheometer and due to deformation and cure progression of DMTA samples. The green dashed line has been shown to indicate the continuity between rheometer and DMTA data. These results show experimentally the expected response predicted by a generalized Maxwell model.

When examining the glassy regime of G' , two important conclusions are observed. First is that the glassy modulus shows a linear dependence on temperature. This implies that the thermo-rheologically simple time-temperature-superposition (horizontal shift only) is not sufficient to describe the viscoelastic material behavior. The second conclusion is that the glassy modulus is shown to be independent of DOC provided the temperature of the material is sufficiently below its instantaneous glass transition temperature ($T_g - T > 50C$).

The results presented in this paper show the connection between rheometry and DMTA tests. In doing so, a methodology and dataset has been generated that can be used to develop a viscoelastic material model that can describe the behavior of a curing thermoset material from pre-gelation to fully cured and over temperatures from $-30^\circ C$ to $250^\circ C$.

These ranges span all DOC and temperatures that are encountered during typical processing of high performance carbon/epoxy composites structures.

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Figure 1: DMTA sample loaded in the 3-point bend geometry.

Figure 2: Storage modulus of MTM45-1 as a function of temperature for various DOC.

Figure 3: Loss modulus from DMTA of MTM45-1 as a function of temperature for various DOC.

Figure 4: Storage modulus of MTM45-1 measured from isothermal rheometer tests.

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Figure 5: Loss modulus of MTM45-1 measured from isothermal rheometer tests.

Figure 8: Storage modulus from rheometer plotted in constant DOC series.

Figure 6: Shear storage modulus MTM45-1 measured from temperature ramp rheometer tests.

Fig. 9. Loss modulus from rheometer plotted in constant DOC series.

Figure 7: Shear loss modulus MTM45-1 measured from temperature ramp rheometer tests.

Figure 10: Overlay of storage modulus from DMTA and rheometer. Green dashed lines show how data connects for constant DOC.

Figure 11: Overlay of loss modulus from DMTA and rheometer. Green dashed lines show how data connects for constant DOC.

[7] C. T. Herakovich “*Mechanics of Fibrous Composites*”. John Wiley & Sons, 1998.

[8] T. A. Bogetti and J. W. Gillespie, Jr, “Process Induced Stress and Deformation in Thick-Section Thermoset Composite Laminates”. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 32, No. 2, pp 179-187, 2001.

References

- [1] M. Haghshenas, R. Vaziri and A. Poursartip “Integrating the simulation of flow and stress development during the processing of thermoset matrix composites”. *Proceedings of ICCM-17*, Edinburgh, Scotland, 2009.
- [2] J. D. Ferry “*Viscoelastic Properties of Polymers*”. John Wiley & Sons, 1980.
- [3] A. Shahkarami and D. Van Ee “Material Characterization for Processing: ACG MTM45-1” *NCAMP. National Institute for Aviation Research*, 15 November 2009. Web. 01 September 2011. http://www.niar.wichita.edu/coe/ncamp_documents/ACG%20MTM45-1/ACGMTM45-1-ProcessingCharacterizationVI-0.pdf
- [4] Convergent Manufacturing Technologies “*RAVEN3*” (Software). (2012)
- [5] J. D. Hughes “The Carbon Fibre/Epoxy Interface – A Review”. *Composite Science and Technology*, 41, 13-45, 1991.
- [6] Umeco Structural Materials (Derby) Ltd. “*Umeco MTM45-1 Data Sheet*” 2012.